

Effect of Academic Resilience on Subjective Well-Being of Students in Islamic Boarding Schools

Fajrina Rahmi, Hasnida, Rr. Lita Hadiati Wulandari

Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

Abstract— This study was to determine the impact of academic resilience toward subjective well-being of students in Islamic Boarding Schools. Data of the study was obtained through a scale of subjective well-being and a scale of academic resilience that has been tested for reliability and validity. The subjects of this study were 87 students in Ma'had Daarut Tahfiz Al-Ikhlâs Islamic boarding schools, consist of 66 male students (75.87%) and 21 female students (24.13%). The results showed that there is impact of academic resilience on subjective well-being of students in Islamic boarding schools. The meaning is, the more academic resilience held by students, the subjective well-being will also increase. And vice versa, if the academic resilience decreases, the level of subjective well-being also decreases. The results of the study are expected to be an input for school stakeholders to increase subjective well-being on their students through resilience academic.

Keywords— Academic resilience, subjective well-being, islamic boarding schools.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the case of education, all citizens ranging from children to parents are entitled to the same rights regardless of social status and so on, that every citizen has the right to education. It was stated that schools should focus on developing student welfare, by making students happy, healthier, more productive and able to develop according to their functions as humans. Student well-being, especially psychological or subjective (well-being), while learning and interacting in school is an important thing and must be realized in every education in formal institutions such as schools. This is important because schools can create conditions for the development of the welfare of their students, both towards positive and negative welfare (Ducket, Sixsmith, & Kagan, 2012; Prasetyo, 2018).

Students who have positive subjective well-being or feel happy in their school are more likely to display a positive impact especially in relation to good academic performance (Turashvili & Japaridze, 2012; Prasetyo, 2018). In a broader context, happy students will have higher life expectancy, be more active, and be far from anxiety and stress (O'Rourke & Cooper, 2010; Prasetyo, 2018). Conversely, when students feel unwell at school, some negative impacts such as school refusal will occur (Ampuni & Andayani, 2017; Prasetyo, 2018).

Acceptance of this condition in psychological terms is known as subjective well-being, which is an assessment that involves cognitive and affective aspects of something that affects the quality of one's life. Diener (2003) states that subjective well-being is someone's subjective evaluation of the life they experience including concepts such as life satisfaction, pleasant emotions, and satisfaction with areas that

affect the level of unpleasant emotions. This subjective evaluation relates to the circumstances and conditions of the hostel which require students to live in a dormitory. So that the positive and negative impacts will affect learning activities and student achievement (Hamdana, 2015).

As for several things that are felt to affect the rest of them one of them is resilience. Resilience is increasingly recognized as an important trait that can be built on students. This construct involves the ability to overcome difficulties and to achieve goals in the face of obstacles (Connor & Davidson, 2003; Aldridge, Fraser, Fozdar, Ala'I, Earnest & Afari 2015). Based on the explanation, there is a research that shows the relationship between resilience and subjective well-being in adolescents at the orphanage conducted by Tsuraya (2017), but it is not yet known the extent of the effect that resilience has on subjective well-being.

The capacity of individuals to maintain their abilities and function competently in dealing with various life stressors is called resilience (VanBreda, 2001; Hendriani, 2018). In line with this understanding, academic resilience is resilience in the learning process, which is a dynamic process that reflects the strength and resilience of a person to rise from negative emotional experiences, when facing difficult situations that are pressing in learning activities undertaken. Academic resilience portrays how students overcome various negative experiences or challenges that are so large, pressing and hindering during the learning process, so that they are able to adapt and carry out any academic demands well (Hendriani, 2018).

Resilience that occurs in students is also called academic resilience. Martin and Marsh (2003) define academic resilience as the ability of students to effectively deal with setbacks, challenges or stresses in an academic context. Another definition was conveyed by Corsini, (2002; Hendriani, 2018) that academic resilience is a term that represents someone's toughness in facing academic difficulties. He will feel and think optimistically, even though he is in a difficulty. Resilient students believe that there is a way out or a solution to the difficulties faced (Chemers, Hu, and Garcia, 2001; Hendriani, 2018). He will also feel challenged to solve various academic difficulties in question. These difficulties encourage resilient individuals to mobilize all the potential so that their competence is growing.

The character of academically resilient individuals is to have social competence, have life skills such as being able to solve problems, being able to think critically, and being able to take initiative during the learning process. Furthermore, it is said that resilient individuals can increase and decrease over time. (Henderson and Milstein 2003; Hendriani: 2018). This is

also supported by research conducted by Amalia and Hendriani (2017) provides data on the challenges and difficulties felt by students studying and living in boarding schools.

Subsequent research found that the subjective well-being condition of students who lived in the dormitories was in the moderate position (middle) with 71.2%. This study also found three main factors that influence positive subjective well-being conditions, namely pleasant friends, fostering independence, and establishing discipline, and three main factors that influence negative subjective well-being conditions, namely dormitory facilities that are still lacking, activities that are too dense and monotonous, as well as angry coaches (Hamdana, 2015).

Based on the results of interpersonal communication, there are also students who feel inadequate with the target set by the school to memorize, even though when selected they are excellent students and have good memorization skills. In the context of student resilience in islamic boarding schools, those who live in it have a different social space from adolescents in general. Activities and values within the islamic boarding schools can be said to have a distinctive style so that the challenges for students in islamic boarding schools are different from non-student even in the same range of development.

Based on the things described above, the researchers want to know the effect of academic resilience on subjective well-being of students in islamic boarding schools.

II. OBJECTIVES AND METHODS

The main purpose of this study was to know the effect of academic resilience on subjective well-being of students in islamic boarding schools. The subjects of this study were 87 students in Ma'had Daarut Tahfiz Al-Ikhlâs islamic boarding schools, consist of 66 male students (75.87%) and 21 female students (24.13%). Data of the study was obtained through a scale of subjective well-being and a scale of academic resilience that has been tested for reliability and validity. The subjective well-being scale is based on two dimensions of subjective well-being according theory from Eid dan Larsen (2003) that is designed and compiled by Halim (2015). The dimensions are life satisfaction (cognitive) and affective. Subjective well-being scale consists of 18 item statements with a reliability level of 0.878.

The academic resilience scale is based on four dimensions of subjective well-being according to Martin dan Marsh (2003) that the statement designed and compiled by Amalia and Hendriani (2017). The dimensions are confidence, control, composure, dan commitment. Academic resilience scale consists of 18 item statements with a reliability level of 0.903. The subjective well-being scale and academic resilience scale used a Likert scale model with five alternative answer choices: 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (neutral), 4 (agree), 5 (strongly agree). Scores for each item correspond to the answers given by the subject. However, on some items in negative statements, the opposite score applies. In this study the analytical method used is simple regression method.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study the hypothesis given is that there is an influence of academic resilience on subjective well-being in students in Islamic boarding schools. In this study the method of analysis used is simple regression method. From the results of data collection on 87 students in Ma'had Daarut Tahfiz Al-Ikhlâs Islamic boarding schools produce the following statistical values:

TABLE I. Regression Result

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	F	Sig.
Regression	935.617	1	14.512	.000
Residual	5480.038	85		
Total	6415.655	86		

Based on the results of the analysis above, a significance value of 0.00 (F arithmetic = 14.512, $p < .05$), indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. It means there is a significant influence of academic resilience on subjective well-being.

Further data analysis is performed to see the effective contribution of academic resilience to subjective well-being. The amount of contributions can be seen from the table below:

TABLE II. R Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	0.382	.146	.136	8.02939

The table above shows the value of the correlation coefficient (R) of .382 and the value of the determinant coefficient (R Square) of .146. This value indicates that the effect of academic resilience on subjective well-being is 14.6%, while the rest (85.4%) is caused by other factors not examined in this study.

Further analysis is carried out to see the regression equation between academic resilience to subjective well-being, which can be seen from the following table:

TABLE III. Regression Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	38.646	7.582	.382	5.097	.000
Academic Resilience	.432	.114		3.809	.000

The regression equation is described by the formula $Y' = B_0 + B_1X_1$, where Y is subjective well-being, while academic resilience is denoted by X_1 . Based on the table above, the regression equation between academic resilience and subjective well-being is $Y' = 38.646 + .432 X_1$. A constant value of 38.646 indicates that if students do not have academic resilience, the subjective well-being consistency value is 38.646. The regression coefficient shows the number 0.432. This means that if academic resilience increases by 1%, then subjective well-being increases by 0.432.

The equation above shows that the direction of influence given academic resilience to subjective well-being is a positive direction. This shows that the higher the academic resilience, the higher the subjective well-being, and vice versa. Based on the regression analysis it can be concluded that the

hypothesis in this study was accepted which means there is a positive influence of academic resilience on subjective well-being.

People who have important goals and strive to achieve them will become more energetic, experience many kinds of positive emotions and will feel that their lives are very meaningful (McGregor & Little; 1998; Nayana, 2013). According to Bernard (1991), the character of individuals who are academically resilient is to have social competence, have life skills such as being able to solve problems, be able to think critically, and be able to take initiative during the learning process. Furthermore, it is said that resilient individuals have a sense of purpose and can see their bright future. They have special interests, life goals, and motivation to achieve the best in education.

The researchers concluded that subjective well-being will change according to the conditions of one's life. Theories other than need and goal satisfaction state that the stability of a person's character can also affect his subjective well-being score. An individual's adaptation to problems in his life becomes a determining factor in subjective well-being scores, whether low or high. This is supported by research conducted by Tsuraya (2017) showing there is a relationship between resilience with subjective well-being in adolescents who are in an orphanage.

Academic resilience is owned by students in various levels of education. Various studies have been carried out to provide an explanation. A number of research results note that academic resilience is related to the magnitude of the challenges at each level of study. According to Rirkin and Hoopman (1991) in Desmita (2009), academic resilience portrays how students overcome various negative experiences or challenges that are so great, pressing and hindering during the learning process, so that they are able to adapt and carry out any academic demands well.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that there is impact of academic resilience on subjective well-being of students in Islamic boarding schools. The implication is, the more academic resilience held by students, the subjective well-being will also increase. And vice versa, if the academic resilience decreases, the level of subjective well-being will also decrease. The results of this study can be input for schools, especially Islamic boarding schools in order to consider academic resilience factors in increasing the subjective well-being of their students.

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